

THE CHALLENGES UZBEK LEARNERS FACE WHEN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND HOW TO OVERCOME THEM

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Introduction. The role of English around the world as the most widely used language has shown its charm for students who wish to continue their education in higher level. However, eagerness to master English is not simple since learning a new language which is totally different with the first language is not an easy task to do. Indeed, it is a long and complex process which needs patient throughout the learning process. It is due to the fact that a learner needs to pay attention to every single aspect of the new language such as grammar and culture (Brown, 2000)

In reality, many language students are only motivated to learn English at the beginning but become confused and unmotivated during the process of their study due to some reasons. Ghenghesh (2010) pointed out in her study that many factors can cause the decrease of student motivation which are grouped into two factors, those are: 1) inside school factors involving students and teacher such as low achievement throughout the process of learning, the feeling of being unable to achieve the learning target and students' efforts that have not been maximal, difficult material, teaching methods and techniques, 2) outside school factors such as the influence of family and friends, and learning activities outside the school time.

Literature Review. This research also discovered that learners who believe their English is terrible feel more uncomfortable and are less ready to speak accurately. Also, Students who believe their English is "bad" are more uncomfortable and hesitant to communicate in English lessons than learners who believe their English is "ok" or "very good." It is revealed that, as described by teachers, the most significant area of difficulty is the linguistic domain (discourse, pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary) since the students have not yet reached a sufficient level in the primary skills of the language (Al-Lawati, 1995). It is due to their perception of a curriculum that does not give a fair chance to learn and practice new and different languages and a lack of variation in assignments planned for teaching grammar. As a result, students cannot improve their speaking skills, particularly given the enormous number of people in a classroom.

Research Methodology. This is a qualitative inquiry using phenomenology approach which was conducted to explore a phenomenon happened among foreign language learners. Phenomenology concerned with “a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasise the importance of personal perspective and interpretation” (Lester, 1999, p. 1). This study was conducted in English language centres where the participants are English language learners with 10 students joining this inquiry. They were participated without coercion. At first, the researcher conducts close observation in their classes, and then explained that the researcher intended to undergo a research about students’ problem in learning English. After that, the researcher asked who wanted to join in this research and 10 students were willing to participate. This research used purposive sampling as all participants that were allowed to participate were students who had problems in learning English. Purposive sampling refers to identify or select individuals as participants who are experiencing the phenomenon of the study (Palinkas et al., 2015)

Sample Size and Selection. This research used a semi structured interview to collect data from participants. Interview was chosen in order to get rich data from participants (Newton, 2010). The interview contains questions regarding students’ problem in learning English and how they cope with their problem. These questions were used to answers the research questions. In the process of collecting data, the interview session was recorded and later it was transcribed before it was analysed.

Data Analysis. After collecting participant’s data, the data were analysed using thematic analysis as one of the techniques in analysing quantitative data. Six techniques of Braun & Clarke were applied in the process of data analyse, those are: 1) becoming familiar with the data by re-reading it, 2) generating initial codes, 3) searching for themes, 4) reviewing the themes, 5) defining the themes, 6) starting to write the findings (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017, p. 3354).

Discussion of Results. It has been called the "Rome of the East," "Eden of Ancient East," and "The Pearl of the Silk Road." Uzbekistan has been renowned for its Silk Route cities and dazzling natural beauty. Samarkand enjoyed great glory during the height of trade along the Silk Road, beginning in the 2nd century and lasting until the 16th century. This country has a rich heritage and ethnicity, and history buffs are always fascinated by it. There are remnants of an area occupied by Alexander the Great and Genghis Khan. Additionally, Babur, the founder of the Mughal dynasty in India, belonged to Uzbekistan, so the country had a close relationship with India. That relationship continues to this day in terms of mutual interest and understanding. With a circumference twice as large as the United Kingdom, this country boasts an ancient history and rich culture. By the mid 19th

century, Russia and Britain were both trying to gain control of Central Asia: Russia from the north and Britain from India in the south. Isolated since the time of the Silk Routes, Central Asia had not seen Western visitors for hundreds of years. During 18th century Russia gained control of much of the region and it continued till 1992.

USSR (Union of Soviet Socialist Republics) has had some influence on the culture and the language of the people in the region, and the majority speaks Uzbek, Russian and Turkish. As far as Uzbek concern, it belongs to the south-eastern, or Chagatai, branch of the Turkic languages. Most people in this country are either bilingual or trilingual, but English is a hard nut to crack for years. Did you ever wonder why adapting English is considered so strenuous here?

First and foremost, in this merry land, English language has been unable to make any impact at all among the people, unlike say in India, where English words are part of daily conversations. Many of us would speak ‘Hinglish’, for example, rather than pure Hindi. As far as Uzbekistan is concerned, it is very evident that all of the sign boards, shop window, signage, pay bill, flier etc. are all purely in Uzbek only. What more can say that, gadgets as well as electronic devices are widely used in either in Uzbek or in Russian. In addition, most students are not motivated to learn the English language because their teachers are not well-trained or not sufficiently qualified; for example, many of them use Uzbek language while teaching, so they cannot perform well to attract the interest of the student. In this case, teachers are unable to fill the void left by parents who are illiterate in English. Moreover, any stimulation is driven by necessity, or in other words, motivation arises from necessity. Here, it is plain as a pikestaff that once the region became a part of the USSR, the English language was not as motivating as it is now for the people. Because, the Russian language was good enough for commoners and elites alike to explore and grow, and many technical and scientific terms were solely in Russian.

On the other hand, in the aftermath of Uzbekistan's independence, the scenario has changed. The country has recognized the importance of the English language to attract the world and is making all possible efforts to bring about changes. In recent decades, English has become an indispensable part of the country's primary and secondary school curriculum. It is not only a matter of being a compulsory subject within the school curriculum but it is also an area of study that many pupils want to develop to excel the career opportunities. A notable example of this is the mushrooming of IELTS centers and English learning institutes. As a result, it is popular for those who know English to get a job faster and receive more remuneration. What is more, the Uzbek government offers \$4,000 in Presidential Schools to teachers who are proficient in English. In a nutshell, there is a trend across

the nation that English is the language of dignity and the English-speaking people are respected.

In light of the above, it is obvious that the demand for English language courses is escalating day by day. In response to this, government of Uzbekistan has launched an initiative to offer intensive English training at schools by recruiting foreign English teachers. Private universities formed the curriculum to meet the requirements of the Uzbekistan government guidelines and to help students obtain desirable employment.

Conclusion. As students from non-English speaking background, Uzbek students experience complicated process during the learning process. It is due to the fact that English language is not used in daily life. Furthermore, linguistically and culturally, English and Uzbek are different one another in their structure. Based on the findings of this research, the burdensome experienced by students occurs as the result of linguistic distinction which impact their mastery of English. In order to address their problem to improve their language proficiency, in this study, students applied different ways. On top of that, most students choose to deal with their problem by conducting autonomous learning and using technology. In this learning autonomy, they try not to count on the teachers totally. Students try to decide their own way of learning which are suitable for them and becoming more engaged in learning the target language (Balcikanli, 2010). In addition, technology invasion also has positive effect for students to build their own learning. In short, this study has raised the phenomenon of problems faced by Uzbek students. However, due to limited time, the researcher only focuses on students' problem in developing their language skills whereas there are still many factors of difficulties in learning foreign language such as students' anxiety and motivation. The other problem is the participants come from two education centres. Therefore, it cannot represent all Uzbek students in general.

In conclusion, mother tongue cannot be separated because it's like mother's milk. But, Uzbekistan urges the improvement of English in order to not only grow its economy but also to impress visitors with its uniqueness and make its mark among other countries.

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